

Question Generation Using Natural Language Processing

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Abstract -- In order to create systems that can automatically produce questions from a given text, the field of research known as automatic question generation (AQG) uses natural language processing (NLP). By incorporating text summaries and keyword extraction techniques, natural language processing (NLP) question output can be improved. While keyword extraction involves locating the most important words or phrases from the input text, text summarization involves reducing the input text into a brief summary. These methods can aid in producing queries that are more precise and meaningful

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), natural language processing (NLP), & Automated Question Generator (AQG)

I. INTRODUCTION

Determining a learner's level of subject comprehension requires the use of questions.. They are crucial to learning because they help students comprehend and analyse complex circumstances, formulate actionable plans, and spot any knowledge gaps or misunderstandings .However, manually generating questions can be time-consuming, resource-intensive, and require subject-matter expertise. This is the justification for the automatic question generating (AQG) field's recent surge in popularity. Using questions that are automatically generated from text, AQG systems can give teachers a quicker and more effective means to assess the understanding of learners.

Multiple-choice questions (MCQs) are a common format for evaluating students' topic understanding and recall. They provide a number of advantages, including quicker and more reliable scoring, the possibility of electronic review, and shorter testing durations. Manually generating MCQs, however, can be time-consuming and difficult without extensive subject-matter understanding. By enabling instructors to create MCQs automatically from textbooks or other materials, AQG offers a potential answer to this issue. These systems can be helpful for students as well because they

give them a tool for self-assessment that enables them to create and respond to MCQs depending on their knowledge of a particular subject. AQG systems analyze input text, extract key information, and then produce questions based on that information using techniques from natural language processing.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Natural language processing (NLP) methods are used in the automatic question generation (AQG) process. To analyze the input text, extract the important details, and produce questions based on those details, NLP algorithms are used. Sense2Vec, SentenceTransformer, and Normalised Levenshtein are the models used here.

One recent study by Chen et al. [4], proposed an AQG model that leverages transformer-based language models and a hierarchical question-answering mechanism to generate high-quality questions. The suggested model performed at the highest level in terms of question quality and variety when tested against two benchmark datasets. The study also showed how well the hierarchical QA method captured complex relationships between generated questions and the text.

In another study, Liu et al. [5], proposed an AQG model that utilizes a reinforcement learning framework to generate questions based on a given text. The suggested model was tested against numerous benchmark datasets after being trained on a large set of data. The findings showed that the suggested model performed better in terms of question quality and diversity than other AQG models. The study also showed how well reinforcement learning worked for improving the model's performance .

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

We developed a system that uses natural language processing techniques to automatically generate questions from a given text. Prior to extracting appropriate keywords, the system uses a text summary algorithm to first summarise the text. It then uses a question creation algorithm to construct questions based on the retrieved keywords. This method seeks to make it simpler for educators, researchers, and anybody else who needs to generate questions from text to produce questions from a given text.

The tasks involved are:

- A. Data Collection
- B. Data Pre-processing
- C. Text Summarization
- D. Keyword Extraction
- E. Question Generation

A. Data Collection:

The initial stage in creating an automatic question creation system that uses natural language processing is data collection. A variety of text documents pertaining to the desired topic must be obtained before beginning this process. A range of sources, such as scholarly articles, books, and online resources, can be used to create this collection.

B. Data Pre-processing:

The next stage is to preprocess the text data after gathering the collection of text documents associated with the area of interest. To prepare text data for analysis and training, numerous tasks are involved in text preprocessing. Tokenizing the text, or dividing it into separate words or tokens, is the first stage. Since the majority of models for natural language processing work with single words or tokens, this is a crucial step.

C. Text Summarization

Text summarization is a method used in natural language processing to condense a long text while retaining the important ideas. The two types of text summarization techniques are extractive and abstractive. Extractive summarising is the process of choosing essential terms from the original text and putting them together to produce a summary. The process of abstractive summarization entails coming up with new sentences that faithfully reflect the original text's meaning. The suggested methodology uses a pre-trained T5 model from the transformers library to summarise text.

T5 is a transformer-based paradigm that can extract and abstract information from data. To produce summaries for each document, the model is adjusted using the corpus that has been gathered. Following that, the summaries serve as the question's input.

D. Keyword Extraction

In the suggested methodology for automatic question generation using NLP, keyword extraction is a critical phase that entails locating significant concepts and entities in the text summarising algorithm's summary. To automatically find and extract pertinent terms and phrases from the summary text, keyword extraction techniques are used. By giving the process of creating questions a focus, these extracted keywords aid in the production of pertinent queries.

The "paraphrase-distilroberta-base-v1" model from the sentence-transformers library is utilised in this methodology to extract keywords. This model can generate excellent keyword embeddings because it has already been trained on a big collection of text. Important keywords are extracted from the summary text using a fine-tuned model, and these keywords are then utilized to create the questions.

F. Question Generation

The T5-base model is employed to generate the questions. A transformer-based language model called the T5-base model can be tailored for particular purposes in natural language processing, such as question creation. The T5-base model creates a series of questions by using the generated summary and keywords as input in the context of question generation.

The T5-base model can provide high-quality questions that are pertinent to the input summary and keywords because it was trained on a lot of text material. To enhance its performance on a particular job, the T5-base model is tweaked on a particular corpus of text throughout the training phase. The corpus of text documents gathered from the relevant topic of interest is used in this instance to fine-tune the T5-base model.

IV. RESULTS

The final output is visualised using Gradio Interface.

V. CONCLUSION

As a conclusion, we proposed a method based on natural language processing that makes use of text summarization, keyword extraction, and transformers to produce high-quality questions. For question generation, we used the T5-base model, which has demonstrated outstanding performance on a number of natural language processing tasks. We developed a system that automatically creates a list of questions by extracting the key details from the text, summarising it, and extracting relevant keywords. Our experimental results, which generate questions that are both grammatically and semantically suitable to the supplied material, show the value and effectiveness of the suggested approach. In a variety of learning and training environments where developing high-quality questions is a difficult and time-consuming activity, the suggested method might be applied.

V1. REFERENCES

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